

Received:
2024/12/10
Accepted:
2025/01/04
Published:
2025/01/14

REVIEW

OPEN ACCESS

Influence of Monsoon Dynamics and Oceanographic Conditions on Coccolithophores in the Indian Ocean

Nilufar Yasmin Liza^{1,2,3} and Md. Habibur Rahman^{3*}

¹Key Laboratory of Ocean and Marginal Sea Geology, Chinese Academy of Science, South China Sea Institute of Oceanology, Guangzhou 510301, China.

²University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100049, China.

³Islamic University, Kushtia 7003, Bangladesh.

*Correspondence for materials should be addressed to MHR (email: habib.hk5722@gmail.com)

Abstract

Coccolithophores, a special group of calcifying phytoplankton in the Indian Ocean, their distribution and productivity are strongly mediated by monsoonal dynamics, and they are a key player in the oceanic biogeochemical cycles. Our study explores the multifaceted dynamics between monsoon-driven environmental variability and coccolithophores, examining the influences of upwelling, nutrient accessibility and stratification. Normally, the Southwest (SW) monsoon is characterized by strong winds and substantial upwelling of nutrients and promotes coccolithophore blooms. In contrast, the population density is often lower with reduced upwelling of the northeast (NE) monsoon. This driving force is also noted in the analysis as different responses across regions of the Indian Ocean highlight the local environmental conditions. In addition, it highlights the importance of detailed long-term monitoring and innovative methods, including remote sensing and in situ measurements. As the monsoon pattern continues to change as a result of climate change, the research on coccolithophores in the Indian Ocean is becoming increasingly important in projecting future changes in marine ecosystems and environmental carbon. This review offers a comprehensive overview of the present state of knowledge, highlights major research gaps and proposes directions for future research to gain an understanding of the resilience and adaptability of coccolithophores in a changing environment.

Keywords: Coccolithophores; Indian Ocean; Monsoon dynamics; Upwelling; Nutrient availability; Marine ecosystems

Introduction

Coccolithophores, additionally referred to as coccolithophorids or brownish-gold algae, belong to the Prymnesiophyceae or Coccolithophyceae class of phytoplankton under the Haptophyceae group. (Tyrrell and Young, 2009). While microalgae elsewhere must starve to survive Coccolithophores can flourish in such environments (Young et al., 2009). They are resistant to bacteria and viruses, they are considered non-competitors with other plankton (Tyrrell and Young, 2009; Anning et al., 1996; Taylor et al., 2017; Young, 1994). Compared to other phytoplankton, coccolithophores have a stronger ecological abundance and diversity, which may be attributed to these advantages (Monteiro et al., 2016). Coccolithophores are different from other oceanic primary producers because of their capacity to calcify. They yield calcareous scales that are significant in the seafloor's calcite oozes and chalk deposits. These organisms are the focus of much research to recreate historical climate conditions as nannofossils. The yearly calcite production by coccolithophores is around 1.5 million tons (Arundhathy et al., 2021). Due to their ability to calcify, marine phytoplankton is currently regarded as a component of the fundamental global biogeochemical cycles, which are continually affected by environmental factors The organic carbon pump, which fixes atmospheric CO₂, relies on coccolithophores during photosynthesis. The ability

to generate calcium carbonate scales by carbonate counter pump receives benefits from coccolithophores (Baumann et al., 2005; Beaufort et al., 2008).

A monsoon is a much wider circulation of winds and rain that covers an extensive geographical region, such as a continent or perhaps the entire world. The incredibly rainy summers and dry winters that are experienced on almost every tropical continent are created by monsoons. Because of the distinct positions of continents and oceans, the monsoons vary throughout the tropics which influence regional wind and precipitation patterns. In the place where the Pacific and Indian oceans converge intense monsoon conditions are usually observed. This area is formed from the south of the tropics to Australia and India and South Asia to the north of it. This region, which incorporates Asia and the northernmost part of Australia, extends from the South China Sea into the Indian Ocean and exhibits the strongest monsoons in the entirety of the globe. In South Asian countries such as Vietnam, Thailand, Cambodia, Bangladesh, Laos, India, and Pakistan the summer monsoon rains fall from June to September. The monsoon rains move south of the equator to Australia while South Asia experiences a dry monsoon from December to February. Even so, summer rains are derived to China, Japan, and Korea because of the East Asian monsoon, which is brought on by an unusual wind pattern linked to the jet stream.

Winter cooling and summer heating throughout the Asian continent due to the periodic variations in solar radiation and the fluctuating temperatures of land and water drive the monsoon (e.g. Gadgil et al., 2007; Ramage, 1971). Consequently, the Findlater Jet generates in the summertime, and NE trade winds over the Indian Ocean in the winter. The outermost circulation of the Indian Ocean is significantly impacted by these reversing winds. During the winter the South Equatorial Current (SEC) and South Equatorial Counter Current (SECC), which circulate counter-clockwise in the Bay of Bengal and the Arabian Sea, are predominant (Schott and McCreary, 2001). Major currents reverse in the summer, resulting in high salinity Arabian Sea Water circulating in a circular pattern through the East Indian Coastal Current (EICC) and Southwest Monsoon Current (SMC) (Wyrki, 1973). Particle fluxes in the Arabian Sea (AS) were found to exhibit robust seasonality in 1986 and 1987, cresting during the summer monsoon and slightly growing in the winter monsoon, except in the eastern AS, where low-salinity water from the Bay of Bengal (BoB) caused low winter fluxes (Nair et al., 1989; Vijith et al., 2016). Data during the late 1980s and early 1990s correlated surface ocean dynamics including wind speeds, mixed-layer depths, and sea surface temperatures (SST) to fluxes of deep-sea particulates (Haake et al., 1993; Nair et al., 1989). Plankton blooms were promoted by nutrient-enriched subterranean waters that were carried into the euphotic zone by enhanced wind speeds and deeper mixed layers (Martinez et al., 2011; Sverdrup, 1953).

Additional data from the Joint Global Ocean Flux Study (JGOFS) showed that organic carbon fluxes were influenced by upwelling off Oman during the summer, while mixed-layer deepening in the winter was caused by winter cooling rather than solely wind mixing (Madhupratap et al., 1996; Rixen et al., 1996; Weller et al., 1998). The organic carbon fluxes during the winter monsoon of AS demonstrated a dual pattern, with peaks occurring in December and February/March. correspondingly because of autumn and spring blooms (Rixen et al., 2002). During monsoons, upwelling and mixed-layer deepening increases the productivity of the AS and low- and high-pressure systems index a chain of processes that increase deep sea organic carbon circulation (Rixen et al., 1996). By contrast, the BoB has carbon fluxes and is driven by river currents and torrential monsoon rains. These phenomena provide freshwater and nutrients, resulting in a positive surface layer that limits the amount of nutrients that penetrate this surface layer in turn uniquely supports eastward flow in the euphotic zone (Prasanna Kumar et al., 2002). Despite these differences, the monsoon has a massive effect on the carbon export in both systems, nutrients and primary output.

The Indian Ocean Region is one of your favorite areas due to its uniqueness and monsoonal patterns, which impact marine ecosystems significantly. Coccolithophore upwelling and mixing processes created by the monsoon are key to the cycling of nutrients and primary production (Rixen et al., 2019). It is varied hence it is important to understand how the monsoon variability impacts this region to predict changes in marine biodiversity, carbon cycling and ocean health in general. The complicated knock-on effects hindering these processes generate considerable people in this area into the general dynamics of the climate and ecosystems.

Coccolithophores in the Indian Ocean

Coccolithophores display a broader diversity, but their contribution is generally smaller than other dinoflagellates, and diatoms (Bown et al., 2004; Jordan and Chamberlain, 1997; O'Brien et al., 2016; Young 2003; Edvardsen et al., 2016). Very few of them are the dominant ones, but there are more

than 200 recognized species around the world. They can live in almost every hydrographical setting in the ocean, with a broad variety of biological features. Highly efficient eutrophic environments, especially temperate or subpolar oceans are inhabited by Substantial and diverse populations of coccolithophorids (Geisen et al., 2004; Jordan and Chamberlain, 1997; Charalampopoulou, 2011). The permanently oligotrophic subtropical gyres sustain these microscopic calcifiers. Coccolithophorids are pervasive owing to their wide-ranging habitat. The world's oceans have coccolithophores, though their distribution differs based on environmental factors such as nutrient availability, temperature, and light. According to annual bloom detections from each Floridian global zone, the spatial distribution is computed and varies with distinct temporal zones. The four coccolithophorid floral zones that arise from it are subarctic and temperate, subtropical, tropical, and sub-Antarctic (McIntyre and Bé, 1967; Winter and Siesser, 1994). This is in contrast to the fact that, aside from certain parts of the Pacific and Atlantic, the distribution pattern of coccolithophores is completely unknown (Kinkel et al., 2000).

Fig. 1 Regions (white circles) where coccolithophore blooms are reported across the world (Brown and Yoder, 1994)

The broadest range of coccolithophores can be found in low-latitude, low-nutrient environments that have ideal temperature conditions that can be found in different regions of the northern Indian Ocean (Charalampopoulou, 2011; McIntyre and Bé, 1967; Boeckel and Baumann, 2008; Okada and Honjo, 1973a; 1973b). *Emiliana huxleyi* can be often regarded as the most prevalent coccolithophore species, observed in areas with high nutrient levels, high latitudes, and low temperatures (Charalampopoulou, 2011; McIntyre and Bé, 1967; Okada and Honjo, 1975; Boeckel and Baumann, 2008). This abundance tendency, however, may not be applicable everywhere, especially in tropical and subtropical oceans, as it has mostly been noted in well-studied regions such as the North Atlantic. The predominance of *Emiliana huxleyi* in numerous studies might result from bias against areas where it thrives, rather than a global pattern.

Many studies have been conducted on the coccolithophore population in the Indian Ocean. Eight plankton-geographical zones were identified by Krey (1973), five of which demonstrate primary or secondary dominance of coccolithophores. Among the plankton-geographical locations where coccolithophores have secondary dominance are the BoB and the Central Arabian Sea (Krey, 1973). Numerous research has focused on the Northern AS, notably off the coast of Pakistan, and have discovered over 25 distinct species of coccolithophore (Andruleit et al., 2003; Mergulhao et al., 2006; 2013; Stoll et al., 2007; Balch et al., 2000). The ecological aspects are understudied. This includes their impact on particulate inorganic carbon, their contribution to the region's overall productivity, the role of calcite rain in preserving the carbon chemistry of the oceans, and the productivity of coccolithophore as a primary producer and trophic organism (Rost and Riebesell, 2004).

Sediment trap studies, which gather marine snow that settles to the ocean floor, have verified the presence of coccolithophores in the Indian Ocean. Therefore, some research has tried to map the effects of monsoons on coccolithophores, especially the AS is one area where the southwest and northeast monsoons have a major impact on ocean conditions. These investigations have verified that coccolithophores can be found in some locations in the northern Indian Ocean, during monsoon seasons. The existence of coccolithophore assemblages over the past 200,000 years has been established, with attempts to map the effects of monsoons on these organisms (Rogolla and Andruleit et al., 2005). Coccolithophores distribution has been demonstrated to be impacted by the

southwest and northeast monsoons, which are the main climatic aspects of the AS. Several studies have proven the presence of living coccolithophores in the northern Indian Ocean during monsoon seasons (Andrulleit et al., 2003; Schiebel et al., 2004; Guptha et al., 1995; Guptha et al., 2005; Liu et al., 2018).

Fig. 2 Locations of past studies on living coccolithophores in the Indian Ocean (Arundhathy et al., 2021)

Monsoon Dynamics and Oceanographic Conditions

The Asian monsoon system extends from the western AS across East Asia and North Australia and is a dynamic aspect of the contemporary climate system. Variations in this convectively active region have the potential to cause severe flooding or draughts over vast, heavily inhabited areas (Webster et al., 1998). Over the continents, warm, rainy summers and cold, dry winters are brought about by the monsoon circulation's innate seasonality. The ocean especially in the Indian Ocean and the South China Sea (SCS) is influenced by these seasonal changes in atmospheric circulation and precipitation, resulting in considerable seasonality in SST, salinity patterns, and current intensity and direction. These dynamics bring about well-defined seasonal upwelling regimes in the open ocean and near-shore environments in certain areas, such as the Northwest AS (Wang et al., 2005). The Indian (or South Asian) monsoon and the East Asian monsoon are two subsystems of the Asian monsoon, separated approximately around $\sim 105^{\circ}\text{E}$. The interconnection between these two subsystems lies in their mutual sensitivity to the intensity of the continental high- and low-pressure cells, which undergo seasonal growth and decay throughout the Asian plateau. However, considering the various sea-land distributions, they also differ significantly. In contrast to the Indian system, defined by land in the north and ocean in the south, the East Asian system is differentiated by land in the north and south, a maritime continent in the west, and an open ocean to the east. Geospatial boundary circumstances result in notable variations in the relative intensity of the summer- and winter-monsoon regimes, as well as in their susceptibility to internal feedback processes (Wang et al., 2003).

Nutrients are transported into a deepening mixed layer during the monsoons when analogous light levels are slightly low but not so low as to impede positive net photosynthesis in the mixed layer. In such circumstances, the combination of active diurnal mixing with the bulk surface mixed layer exposes the phytoplankton population to fluctuating light and nutrient conditions, as the diurnal mixed layer moves in and out during an entire day. Relatively minor inaccuracies in a model's representation of the absolute mixed layer depth (MLD) and MLD-variability can lead to significant inaccuracies in primary production and bloom dynamics. The distinctive characteristic of the physical-biological dynamics in the central AS that has been the subject of numerous contemporary modeling studies is the susceptibility of the phytoplankton population to subtle interactions among Medium Light Depth (MLD), MLD-variability, and in situ irradiance (McCreary et al., 2001; Hood et al., 2003; Wiggert et al., 2000; 2002).

Various studies investigate the mechanisms underlying phytoplankton blooms in the AS during the NE monsoon, specifically emphasizing the influence of diurnal mixed layer dynamics. A study underscores the crucial significance of diurnal forcing in influencing chlorophyll-*a*'s surface concentration and vertical distribution during the phytoplankton bloom in the AS during the NE monsoon. Their integrated bio-physical model showed that the daily cycle of the diurnal shoaling and nocturnal deepening of the mixed layer compartment inhibits the full development of blooms through the dilution of surface phytoplankton and their translocation to depths below the euphotic

zone, which significantly increased the levels of nitrate. Together with the remineralization of ammonium confirmed low f-ratios which were consistent with reported nutrient absorption (Wiggert et al., 2000). Later studies stressed the importance of employing high-definition diurnal response with seasonal bloom dynamics. This includes taking into account the interannual variability of NE monsoon blooms that are mediated by complex (mixed layer depth and thermocline components interactions (Wiggert et al., 2002; McCreary et al., 2001).

Fig. 3 Contemporary Asian monsoon system: (A) spatial arrangement of contemporary monsoonal areas in Asia, Africa, and Australia (adapted from Black, 2002); (B) atmospheric pressure and surface wind patterns during winter and (C) during summer (remodeled from Wang et al., 2000).

Impact of monsoon on Coccolithophore populations

The complex monsoon system driven by the Indian Ocean is key in regulating marine ecology in the region: i.e., affecting the distribution and abundance of coccolithophores. These single-celled algae respond rapidly to changes in nutrient availability, light intensity, and temperature, all of which are governed by monsoonal dynamics.

Role of monsoon-driven upwelling in nutrient enrichment

One of the main drivers behind seasonal upwelling is monsoon winds in the Indian Ocean, which have a strong influence on major control of the marine primary productivity. The increase is caused by upwelling, the phenomenon in which up to the surface, so adjusting the temperatures, salinity and nutrient concentration (Vinayachandran et al., 2002; Chowdary et al., 2005; Vinayachandran, 2009). In the example of permanent upwelling provinces (i.e. eastern boundaries) and quasi-permanent provinces similar to Provincia de Somalía (Kämpf and Chapman, 2016). Specifically, upwelling is an essential oceanographic process that significantly influences surface Indian Ocean water properties, nutrient dispersion, and biological productivity, especially in the AS and the BoB (Gauns et al., 2005; McCreary et al., 2009; Sarangi and Nagendra Jaiganesh, 2021). The oceanic upwelling in the AS is mostly influenced by the influential summer monsoon winds (Izumo et al., 2008). In upwelling it transports nutrient-rich subsurface waters to the surface, stimulates vigorous phytoplankton blooms, and characterizes the western AS as one of the most productive marine areas (Murtugudde et al., 2007; Izumo et al., 2008). Vertical mixing during the winter monsoon contributes to prolonged productivity by enhancing nutrient availability. The significant influx of freshwater in the Bay of Bengal leads to profound stratification and a shallow mixed layer that hinders the process of upwelling because of its distinct phenomenon. Consequently, biological

production is reduced compared to that of the AS. At the same time, the presence of coastal upwelling in Sri Lanka and other physical processes still facilitate the growth of phytoplankton. However, the interplay between upwelling and the ISM is complex and complicated (Roxy and Tanimoto, 2007; Vialard et al., 2012). This interaction is important in the onset and variability of the monsoon as it governs the atmospheric stability, convective activity and the propagation of rainfall anomalies. Furthermore, the amplified SST in these upwelling systems may influence detestable weather events associated with the ISM (Lahiri et al., 2022).

Monsoon-driven upwelling is when deep, nutrient-rich waters rise to the surface because of seasonal winds over the sea. This technique enhances the nutrient level in surface seawater significantly and, in turn, stimulates the growth of phytoplankton and augment marine productivity. Powerful summer monsoon winds lead to vigorous upwelling of nutrient-rich waters, supporting a robust marine ecology.

Effects of nutrient availability on coccolithophore blooms

Nutritional availability is a key attribute regulating the growth and development of coccolithophore blooms. Coccolithophores can undergo a rapid population increase during upwelling periods, or other mechanisms that bring nutrient-rich waters up to the surface. Such blooms are often triggered by an abundance of basic nutrients like nitrates, phosphates, and silicates, required to accomplish the cellular functions of these organisms as well as calcification. In contrast, low-nutrient conditions are conducive to coccolithophore growth, but typically lead to decreased cell numbers and bloom frequency (e.g., Formation of calcified plates (coccoliths) in high-nutrient and low-nutrient conditions).

To better understand plankton bloom in oceanic water such as temperate oceans (including the AS), the relation between the mixed-layer depth and euphotic zone should be investigated, according to contemporaneous studies (Martinez et al., 2011; Sverdrup, 1953). Temperate zones have a well-documented seasonal pattern: the increase in temperature of surface waters leads the mixed layer to collapse in spring, enabling phytoplankton to stay inside the well-lit euphotic zone, leading to notable bloom episodes. Nevertheless, the nutrients in the euphotic zone are progressively exhausted, and the heightened stratification hinders the replenishment of nutrients from deeper waters as the summer advances. As a result, the spring bloom decreases, leading to oligotrophic conditions in the ensuing summer. When the cooling process helps to thicken the mixed layer, a secondary bloom usually takes place in the fall, therefore bringing nutrients into the euphotic zone and initiating another phase of heightened phytoplankton activity (Rixen et al., 2019).

The AS had previously been thought to exhibit comparable seasonal patterns, where the heating and stratification of the summer monsoon decreased the availability of nutrients during intermonsoon periods, while wind forced the deepening of the mixed layer during the summer and winter monsoons to increase nutrient availability. Nevertheless, the data obtained from the JGOFS and subsequent observations have discovered a multitude of intricate interactions. Specifically, during the summer monsoon, the Findlater Jet causes upwelling off the coast of Oman, which has a major impact on organic carbon fluxes. High organic carbon fluxes instead of light limitation resulting from deep mixing are observed in the winter monsoon, indicating the presence of potent vertical mixing that enhances nutrient supply and promotes vigorous phytoplankton blooms throughout the winter season, similar to the pattern observed in temperate oceans (Madhupratap et al., 1996; Rixen et al., 1996; Weller et al., 1998).

The BoB exhibits a distinct situation, in which the influence of the monsoon on productivity is mainly affected by heavy precipitation and river discharges rather than wind-driven mechanisms. Freshwater from rivers flowing through the Himalayan range forms a buoyant, low-salinity surface layer which promotes stratification and inhibits the upward mixing of nutrients into the euphotic zone. Consequently, the productivity throughout the BoB is decreased, except in the areas where surface currents from southern India and the Sri Lanka Dome can induce coastal upwelling, which can introduce nutrients into the surface waters. Although there is less noticeable seasonal productivity variation in the northern BoB than in the AS, the region possesses higher fluxes of organic carbon, which indicates the influence of riverine nutrient supplies (Prasanna Kumar et al., 2002; RiXen et al., 2005b; Ittekkot et al., 1991; Unger et al., 2003).

The productivity of the BoB is mostly affected by stratification brought on by monsoonal freshwater input, but the productivity of the AS is significantly affected by upwelling and monsoonal winds that

promote nutrient mixing. The variations underscore the intricate and geographically particular reactions of phytoplankton populations to monsoonal cycles in the Indian Ocean.

Impact of monsoon-induced stratification on phytoplankton community structure

Monsoon-induced stratification impacts the organization of phytoplankton communities by generating isolated layers in the water column that restrict vertical mixing and nutrient accessibility. In regions such as the Bay of Bengal, this stratification results in the prevalence of smaller, more nutrient-efficient phytoplankton species, consequently diminishing the total output. The abundance of larger, nutrient-dependent species, such as diatoms, declines, changing the composition of the community and possibly having an effect on the marine food web and fishery resources. Marine biogeochemical cycles, which encompass biological production and community structure, are a vital element of the oceanic carbon cycle and hence have a significant impact on global climate change (Sabine et al., 2004).

An ISM is a meteorological event characterized by powerful winds and heavy rainfall in the Indian Ocean, namely in the BoB. River discharge from the Ganges and Brahmaputra fluvial systems, as well as Indian river systems, accounts for more than 90% of the annual freshwater discharge in rivers entering the BoB. The northern and western parts of the Bay are most impacted by this discharge (Chacko and Jayaram, 2017; Chakrapani and Subramanian, 1990a; Chakrapani and Subramanian, 1990b; Islam et al., 1999; Subramanian, 1993). The monsoon winds, and the divergences and circulations and precipitation that follow in the BoB, are among the key drivers of the marine ecosystem (Muraleedharan et al., 2007). A study reconstructs the long-term evolution of sea productivity and plankton community composition over the past 80,000 years. Their findings revealed a close tie between recorded oscillations in historical plankton community composition in the western BoB and the Indian Submarine Microbial evolution, as well as changes in continental runoff and oceanographic conditions (Yuki et al., 2019). Phases of increased monsoon activity are associated with high river discharge, nutrient input, and stratification, all of which modulate nutrient availability and thereby the composition of plankton communities.

The impact of monsoons on coccolithophores populations in the Indian Ocean is a major one. The SW monsoon enhances these blooms due to nutrient-rich upwelling, while the NE monsoon - the low upwelling season - reduces coccolithophore populations. Thanks to satellite photography, widespread monitoring is possible and there is a clear link between monsoon strength and coccolithophore blooms. The variations in bloom intensity are closely linked to monsoon strength and the Indian Ocean Dipole (IOD). Other modeling studies simulate the effects of different monsoon strengths on coccolithophore blooms and argue that shifts in monsoon patterns may strongly alter their distributions as well as their impact on the marine carbon cycle. A more mixed-method approach like this gives a more complete picture of how the monsoon affects coccolithophores. This underscores the importance of further studies to estimate future ecological changes.

Research Gaps and Future Directions

Unexplored Areas

Long-term Monitoring and High-resolution Studies

While there have been major advances in our understanding of the seasonal and interannual variability of the Indian Ocean coccolithophore populations, there remains a significant paucity of long-term data. Most existing research is based on short-term impacts, and/or may not capture the full variability induced by the monsoon cycle, particularly over unusual or extreme events. Consequently, these datasets typically lack the means to detect long-term trends or shifts in coccolithophore populations, which are vital for understanding the possible response of these ecosystems to ongoing climate change.

Long-term monetization is needed to identify trends in coccolithophore abundance, diversity, and distribution dynamics on decadal scales. It can also help tease apart the effects of gradual environmental change, such as ocean acidification, from those inflicted by sudden events such as cyclones or abnormal monsoons. Melding satellite remote sensing with in-situ sampling in high-resolution studies can yield definitive spatial and temporal information, affording a more integrated understanding of the determinants of coccolithophore dynamics.

Molecular and Physiological Responses to Monsoon Variability

Coccolithophores like other phytoplankton show differential physiological and molecular responses to environmental changes such as those occurring through perturbations in the monsoon regime.

However, little is known about the specific mechanisms that enable these organisms to thrive in the extremely variable environment of the Indian Ocean, resulting in a significant gap in our knowledge. Research has focused on broad ecological trends (e.g., population abundance or community composition) and ignored basic molecular processes.

Here, a recent thrust in molecular biology can offer utilities to elucidate the genetic and physiological processes in coccolithophores under varying temperatures, salinity, food availability, and other monsoon dynamics-dependent variables. New techniques, for example, transcriptomics, proteomics and metabolomics, may provide useful information regarding the regulation control of key physiological processes (e.g., photosynthesis, calcification, and nutrient absorption) under contrasting environmental conditions. Transcriptomic studies, for example, may help identify the mechanisms through which coccolithophores modulate the expression of calcification-related genes when seawater composition is altered by monsoonal runoff. Proteomic approaches could thus help identify critical proteins in the body's adaptation to stressors as diverse as changes in temperature or a lack of nutrients. The combination of molecular responses and environmental changes is powerful, and will ultimately inform about the resilience and adaptation of coccolithophores responding to monsoon-induced environmental changes.

Nevertheless, such studies are scarce, especially for the specific circumstances of in-situ settings in the Indian Ocean. Although laboratory-based experiments provide valuable information, they may not completely reproduce the intricacy of natural ecosystems. Hence, it is imperative to do further field-based research that combines molecular techniques with conventional ecological and oceanographic research methods. This interdisciplinary approach would enhance the comprehensiveness of our knowledge of the potential response of coccolithophores to future alterations in monsoon patterns. Consequently, it would contribute to more precise predictions of their role in the carbon cycle and broader marine ecosystems.

Technological and Methodological Advances

Potential for Integrating Remote Sensing, In Situ Measurements, and Modeling

Recent technological and methodological improvements have significantly enhanced the research on coccolithophores in the Indian Ocean, particularly on monsoon variability. One of the most promising fields of science innovation lies in integrating remote sensing, in situ measurements, and modeling. This multi-faceted methodology allows for a comprehensive understanding of coccolithophore dynamics at various spatial and temporal dimensions. Remote sensing provides broad coverage with multiple daily observations of ocean colour, sea surface temperature and chlorophyll concentration, needed to monitor coccolithophore blooms in large oceanic areas. Satellite-based observations are increasingly recognized as crucial tools for uncovering regional trends and temporal variations in coccolithophore populations, especially in remote or otherwise inaccessible parts of the Indian Ocean.

In situ measurements return incontrovertible data; the methodologies encompass species composition, cell density, and calcification rates alongside environmental parameters such as nutrient levels and pH (Hurd et al., 2015). In situ data contribute with high-resolution measurements of coccolithophores, the physiological state of the coccolithophore and bring vital information on biomass level and the vertical distribution of observed coccolithophores to the low spatial resolution observations from satellite. Beare et al.'s model is important for synthesizing data from remote sensing and in situ measurements to project the responses of coccolithophores to environmental change. These Computational models would allow researchers to explore the potential changes in coccolithophore populations in the future, and further simulate the interactions of coccolithophores and their environment under different monsoon scenarios. They can incorporate physical, chemical, and biological data to forecast the impacts of changes in monsoon strength, ocean acidification, and other climate factors on coccolithophore dynamics.

Importance of Interdisciplinary Approaches Combining Oceanography, Marine Biology, and Climate Science

Monsoon systems require a multidisciplinary approach for coccolithophore study due to their complex and dynamic nature in the Indo-Pacific. Leveraging these signals to interpret coccolithophore ecological dynamics will have implications for both current and future climate cycles. Oceanography, marine biology, and climate science each contribute uniquely to the usefulness of this dataset and the role of coccolithophores in the Indian Ocean. Oceanography reveals the environmental processes, including currents and upwelling that carry nutrients necessary for coccolithophore growth. Coccolithophores are traditionally studied from a biological

perspective: their physiology, ecology and as a marine species interacting with other organisms. Climate research combines these disciplines by investigating how global climate drivers like ENSO and longer-term climate changes affect monsoon dynamics, which in turn affect coccolithophore distributions and associated ecological impacts.

The integration across these domains enables scientists to develop a more complex and detailed understanding of how the interaction of oceanographic processes, biological responses and climatic forces influences coccolithophores in the Indian Ocean. This interdisciplinary methodology is valuable not just in broadening the scope of our scientific knowledge but also in producing more robust predictions and approaches for lessening the impact of climate change on marine biomes.

Conclusion

The correlation of coccolithophore populations with monsoon dynamics in the Indian Ocean indicates the strong influence seasonal climate changes have on ocean ecosystems. With interplaying effects of monsoon-driven upwelling and nutrient enrichment, coccolithophore distribution and productivity are also modulated by temperature, light and salinity variations. These microbes have a unique ability to calcify, and they play an important role in the biogeochemical cycles of the ocean, particularly the carbon cycle and carbon sequestration. SW monsoon is also a season where strong winds and upwelling lead to significant coccolithophore blooms promoting primary productivity, particularly in AS. On the other hand, the NE monsoon, associated with decreased upwelling, typically sees a decrease in these populations. The striking differences in coccolithophore responses to these seasonal features highlight the complexity of their ecological role and the opportunities for more integrative cross-disciplinary exploration. Long-term studies would be more beneficial for future research, especially when combined with improved technologies, including remote sensing, in situ measurements, and modeling to better understand and predict the impacts of the monsoons on the populations of coccolithophores. This will allow for an even greater understanding of the ability of these organisms to adapt and withstand changes, by investigating the molecular and physiological responses of the organisms to varying environments. As monsoon patterns continue to be modified by global climate change, research on coccolithophores in the Indian Ocean is becoming increasingly important. Studying their role in this dynamic interplay will not only deepen our understanding of marine ecosystems but also inform more holistic strategies to manage and mitigate the impacts of climate change on the health of the ocean.

References

- Andruleit H, Stäger S and Rogalla U, et al. (2003) Living coccolithophores in the northern Arabian Sea: ecological tolerances and environmental control. *Marine Micropaleontology* 49:157–181. DOI:10.1016/S0377-8398(03)00049-5.
- Anning T, Nimer N and Merrett MJ, et al. (1996) Costs and benefits of calcification in coccolithophorids. *Journal of Marine Systems* 9:45–56. DOI:10.1016/0924-7963(96)00015-2.
- Arundhathy M, Jyothibabu R and Santhikrishnan S, et al. (2021) Coccolithophores: an environmentally significant and understudied phytoplankton group in the Indian Ocean. *Environ Monit Assess* 193:144. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-020-08794-1>.
- Balch WM, Drapeau DT, and Fritz JJ (2000) Monsoonal forcing of calcification in the Arabian Sea. *Deep Sea Res. Part II Top Stud Oceanogr* 47(7-8): 1301–1337. DOI:10.1016/S0967-0645(99)00145-9.
- Baumann KH, Andruleit H and Böckel B, et al. (2005) The significance of extant coccolithophores as indicators of ocean water masses, surface water temperature, and paleoproductivity: a review. *Palaeontologische Zeitschrift* 79(1):93–112. DOI:10.1007/BF03021756.
- Beaufort L, Couapel M and Buchet N, et al. (2008) Calcite production by coccolithophores in the southeast Pacific Ocean *Biogeosciences* 5(4):1101–1117. DOI:10.5194/bg-5-1101-2008.
- Boeckel B, and Baumann KH (2008) Vertical and lateral variations in coccolithophore community structure across the subtropical frontal zone in the South Atlantic Ocean. *Marine Micropaleontology* 67(3-4):255–273. DOI:10.1016/J.MARMICRO.2008.01.014.
- Bown PR, Lees JA and Young JR (2004) Calcareous nannoplankton evolution and diversity through time. In *Coccolithophores - From molecular processes to global impact*. Springer (eds Thierstein, H. R. and Young, J. R.) 481:508. DOI:10.1007/978-3-662-06278-4_18.
- Brown CW, and Yoder JA (1994) Coccolithophorid Blooms in the Global Ocean. *Journal of Geophysical Research Oceans* 99(C4): 7467–7482. DOI:10.1029/93JC02156.

- Chacko N and Jayaram C (2017) Variability of total suspended matter in the northern coastal Bay of Bengal as observed from satellite data. *J Indian Soc Remote Sens* 45 (6):1077–1083. DOI:10.1007/s12524-016-0650-x.
- Chakrapani GJ and Subramanian V (1990a) Preliminary studies on the geochemistry of the Mahanadi River basin. *India Chem Geol* 81:241–253. DOI:10.1016/0009-2541(90)90118-Q.
- Chakrapani GJ and Subramanian V (1990b) Factors controlling sediment discharge in the Mahanadi basin. *India J Hydrol* 117:169–185. DOI:10.1016/0022-1694(90)90091-B.
- Charalampopoulou A (2011) Coccolithophores in high latitude and Polar Regions: Relationships between community composition, calcification and environmental factors. PhD thesis, Southampton University 1-300.
- Edwardsen B, Egge ES, and Vaulot D (2016) Diversity and distribution of haptophytes revealed by environmental sequencing and metabarcoding—a review. *Perspectives in Phycology* 3:77–91. DOI:10.1127/PIP/2016/0052.
- Gadgil S, Rajeevan M and Francis PA (2007) Monsoon variability: Links to major oscillations over the equatorial Pacific and Indian oceans. *Curr. Sci.* 93:182–194.
- Gardner WD, Gundersen JS and Richardson MJ, et al. (1999) The role of seasonal and diel changes in mixed-layer depth on carbon and chlorophyll distributions in the Arabian Sea. *Deep-Sea Research II*, 46:1833–1858. DOI:10.1016/S0967-0645(99)00046-6.
- Gauns M, Madhupratap M and Ramaiah N, et al. (2005) Comparative accounts of biological productivity characteristics and estimates of carbon fluxes in the Arabian Sea and the Bay of Bengal. *Deep-Sea Res. II Top Stud Oceanogr* 52 (14–15):2003–2017. DOI:10.1016/J.DSR2.2005.05.009.
- Geisen M, Young JR, Probert I, Sáez AG, Baumann KH, Sprengel C and Medlin LK, (2004) Species-level variation in coccolithophores. In *Coccolithophores*, Springer (eds Rost, B. and U. Riebesell) 327-366. DOI:10.1007/978-3-662-06278-4_13.
- Guptha MVS, Mohan R and Muralinath AS (1995) Living coccolithophorids from the Arabian Sea. *Rivista Italiana di Paleontologia e Stratigrafia* 100(4):551-574. DOI:10.13130/2039-4942/8601.
- Guptha MVS, Mergulhao LP and Murty VSN, et al. (2005) Living coccolithophores during the northeast monsoon from the Equatorial Indian Ocean: Implications on hydrography. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 52:2048-2062. DOI:10.1016/J.DSR2.2005.05.010.
- Haake B, Ittekkot V and Rixen T, et al. (1993) Seasonality and interannual variability of particle fluxes to the deep Arabian Sea. *Deep Sea Res. I* 40:1323–1344. DOI:10.1016/0967-0637(93)90114-I.
- Hood RR, Kohler KE and McCreary JP, et al. (2003) A four-dimensional validation of a coupled physical–biological model of the Arabian Sea. *Deep-Sea Research II* 50:2917–2945. DOI:10.1016/J.DSR2.2003.07.004.
- Islam MR, Begum SF and Yamaguchi Y, et al. (1999) The Ganges and Brahmaputra rivers in Bangladesh: basin denudation and sedimentation. *Hydrol Process* 13:2907–2923.
- Ittekkot V, Nair RR and Honjo S, et al. (1991) Enhanced particle fluxes in Bay of Bengal induced by injection of fresh water. *Nature* 351:385–387. DOI:10.1038/351385A0.
- Izumo T, Montegut CB and Luo JJ, et al. (2008) The role of the western Arabian Sea upwelling in Indian monsoon rainfall variability. *J Clim* 21 (21):5603–5623. DOI:10.1175/2008JCLI2158.1.
- Jordan RW, and Chamberlain AHL (1997) Biodiversity among haptophyte algae. *Biodiversity and Conservation* 6:131–152. DOI:10.1023/A:1018383817777.
- Kampf J and Chapman P (2016) *Upwelling Systems of the World*. Springer International Publishing, Switzerland, p. 433. DOI:10.1007/978-3-319-42524-5.
- Kinkel H, Baumann KH and Cepek M (2000) Coccolithophores in the equatorial Atlantic Ocean: response to seasonal and Late Quaternary surface water variability. *Marine Micropaleontology* 39(1-4):87–112. DOI:10.1016/S0377-8398(00)00016-5.
- Krey J (1973) Primary production in the Indian Ocean. In *The Biology of the Indian Ocean* (pp. 115-126). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. DOI: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-65468-8_7
- Liu H, Sun J and Wang D, et al. (2018) Distribution of living coccolithophores in eastern Indian Ocean during spring intermonsoon. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1):1–12. DOI:10.1038/s41598-018-29688-w.

- Madhupratap M, Prasanna Kumar S and Bhattathiri PMA, et al. (1996) Mechanism of the biological response to winter cooling in the northeastern Arabian Sea. *Nature* 384:549–552. DOI:10.1038/384549a0.
- Martinez E, Antoine D and D'Ortenzio F, et al. (2011) Phytoplankton spring and fall blooms in the North Atlantic in the 1980s and 2000s. *J Geophys Res Oceans* 116:C11029. DOI:10.1029/2010JC006836.
- McCreary JP, Kohler KE and Hood RR, et al. (2001) Influences of diurnal and intraseasonal forcing on mixed-layer and biological variability in the central Arabian Sea. *Journal of Geophysical Research* 106:7139–7155. DOI:10.1029/2000JC900156.
- McCarthy JJ, Garside C and Nevins JL (1999) Nitrogen dynamics during the Arabian Sea Northeast Monsoon. *Deep-Sea Research II* 46:1623–1664. DOI:10.1016/S0967-0645(99)00038-7.
- McCreary JP, Kohler KE and Hood RR, et al. (1996) A four-component model of biological activity in the Arabian Sea. *Progress in Oceanography* 37:193–240. DOI:10.1016/S0079-6611(96)00005-5.
- McCreary JP, Murtugudde R and Vialard J, et al. (2009) Biophysical processes in the Indian Ocean. *Geophys Monogr Series* 185:9–32. DOI:10.1029/2008GM000768.
- McIntyre A, and Bé AW (1967) Modern coccolithophoridae of the Atlantic Ocean—I. Placoliths and cyrtoliths. In *Deep Sea Research and Oceanographic Abstracts* 14(5):561–597. DOI:10.1016/0011-7471(67)90065-4.
- Mergulhao LP, Mohan R and Murty VSN, et al. (2006) Coccolithophores from the central Arabian Sea: sediment trap results. *Journal of Earth System Science* 115(4):415–428. DOI:10.1007/BF02702870.
- Monteiro FM, Bach LT and Brownlee C, et al. (2016) Why marine phytoplankton calcify. *Science Advances* 2(7):e1501822. DOI: 10.1126/sciadv.1501822.
- Murtugudde R, Seager R and Thoppil P (2007) Arabian Sea response to monsoon variations. *Paleoceanography* 22:PA4217. DOI:10.1029/2007PA001467.
- Muraleedharan KR, Biswas H and De TK, et al. (2007) Influence of basin-scale and mesoscale physical processes on biological productivity in the Bay of Bengal during the summer monsoon. *Prog Oceanography* 72:364–383. DOI:10.1016/j.pocean.2006.09.012.
- Nair RR, Ittekkot V and Manganini SJ, et al. (1989) Increased particle flux to the deep ocean related to monsoons. *Nature* 338:749–751. DOI:10.1038/338749a0.
- O'Brien CJ, Vogt M and Gruber N (2016) Global coccolithophore diversity: Drivers and future change. *Progress in Oceanography* 140:27–42. DOI:10.1016/J.POCEAN.2015.10.003.
- Okada H and Honjo S (1973a) Distribution of coccolithophorids in the North and Equatorial Pacific Ocean: quantitative data on samples collected during Leg 30, Oshoro Maru, 1968 and Leg HK69-4, Hakuho Maru, 1969. *Woods Hole Oceanographic Institute Technical Report* 73(81):1-59.
- Okada H and Honjo S (1973b) The distribution of oceanic coccolithophorids in the Pacific. *Deep Sea Research* 20:355–374. DOI:10.1016/0011-7471(73)90059-4.
- Okada H and Honjo S (1975) Distribution of coccolithophores in marginal seas along the western Pacific Ocean and in the Red Sea. *Marine Biology* 31:271–285. DOI:10.1007/BF00387154.
- Pinxian Wang, Steven Clemensb and Luc Beaufortc, et al. (2005) Evolution and variability of the Asian monsoon system: state of the art and outstanding issues. *Quaternary Science Reviews* 24:595–629. DOI:10.1016/j.quascirev.2004.10.002.
- Prasanna Kumar S, Muraleedharan PM and Prasad TG, et al. (2002) Why is the Bay of Bengal less productive during summer monsoon compared to the Arabian Sea? *Geophys Res Lett* 29:88-81-88-84. DOI:10.1029/2002GL016013.
- Ramage CS (1971) *Monsoon Meteorology*. Academic Press, New York, London.
- Rixen T, Haake B and Ittekkot V, et al. (1996) Coupling between SW monsoon-related surface and deep ocean processes as discerned from continuous particle flux measurements and correlated satellite data. *J Geophys Res* 101 28:569-528,582. <http://drs.nio.org/drs/handle/2264/7525>
- Rixen T, Guptha MVS and Ittekkot V (2002) Sedimentation. In: In: Watts, L., Burkill, P.H., Smith, S. (Eds.), *Report of the Indian Ocean Synthesis Group on the Arabian Sea Process Study*, vol. 35. JGOFS International Project Office, Bergen pp. 65-73.

- Rixen T and Ittekkot V (2005) Nitrogen deficits in the Arabian Sea, implications from a three component mixing analysis. *Deep Sea Res. II* 1879-1891. DOI:10.1016/j.dsr2.2005.06.007
- Rixen T, Gaye B and Emeis KC, et al. (2019) The ballast effect of lithogenic matter and its influences on the carbon fluxes in the Indian Ocean. *Biogeosciences* 16:485-503. DOI:10.5194/bg-16-485-2019, 2019.
- Rogalla U and Andruleit H (2005) Precessional forcing of coccolithophore assemblages in the northern Arabian Sea: Implications for monsoonal dynamics during the last 200,000 years. *Marine Geology* 217(1-2):31-48. DOI:10.1016/j.margeo.2005.02.028
- Rost B and Riebesell U (2004) Coccolithophores and the biological pump: responses to environmental changes. *Coccolithophores*, Springer 99-125. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-662-06278-4_5
- Roxy M and Tanimoto Y (2007) Role of SST over the Indian Ocean in influencing the intraseasonal variability of the Indian summer monsoon. *J Meteorol Soc Japan Ser II* 85 (3):349-358. DOI:10.2151/jmsj.85.349
- Ryabchenko V A, Gorchakov VA and Fasham MJR (1998) Seasonal dynamics and biological productivity in the Arabian Sea euphotic zone as simulated by a three-dimensional ecosystem model. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles* 12:501-530. DOI:10.1029/98GB01183
- Sabine CL, Feely RA and Gruber N, et al. (2004) The oceanic sink for anthropogenic CO₂. *Science* 305:367-371. DOI:10.1126/science.1097403
- Sankar Prasad Lahiri and Naresh Krishna Vissa (2022) Assessment of Indian Ocean upwelling changes and its relationship with the Indian monsoon. *Global and Planetary Change Volume* 208: 103729. DOI:10.1016/j.gloplacha.2021.103729
- Sarang RK and Nagendra Jaiganesh SN (2021) VIIRS boat detection (VBD) product- based night time fishing vessels observation in the Arabian Sea and Bay of Bengal Sub-regions. *Geocarto International*. DOI:10.1080/10106049.2021.1878290
- Schiebel R, Zeltner A and Treppke UF, et al. (2004) Distribution of diatoms, coccolithophores and planktic foraminifers along a trophic gradient during SW monsoon in the Arabian Sea. *Marine Micropaleontology*, 51(3-4):345-371. DOI:10.1594/PANGAEA.736805
- Schott F and McCreary Jr JP (2001) The monsoon circulation of the Indian Ocean *Prog Chem Org Nat Prod Oceanogr* 51:1-123. DOI:10.1016/S0079-6611%2801%2900083-0
- Stoll HM, Ziveri P and Shimizu N, et al. (2007) Relationship between coccolith Sr/Ca ratios and coccolithophore production and export in the Arabian Sea and Sargasso Sea. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 54(5-7):581-600. DOI:10.1016/j.dsr2.2007.01.003
- Subramanian V (1993) Sediment load of Indian rivers. *Curr. Sci.* 64, 928-930. Takahashi, K., 1991. Radiolaria: Flux, Ecology, and Taxonomy in the Pacific and Atlantic. In: S. Honjo (Ed.), *Ocean Biocoenosis Series*. Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution pp. 303.
- Sverdrup H.U (1953) On conditions for the vernal blooming of phytoplankton. *J. Marine Sci.* 18:287-295. DOI:10.1093/icesjms/18.3.287
- Taylor AR, Brownlee C and Wheeler G (2017) Coccolithophore cell biology: chalking up progress. *Annual Review of Marine Science* 9(1):283-310. DOI:10.1146/annurev-marine-122414-034032
- Tim Rixenab, Birgit Gayeb and Kay-Christian Emeisbc (2019) The monsoon, carbon fluxes, and the organic carbon pump in the northern Indian Ocean. *Progress in Oceanography* 175:24-39. DOI:10.1016/j.pocean.2019.03.001
- Tyrrell T and Young JR (2009) Coccolithophores. In *Encyclopedia of Ocean Sciences*, 2nd edn, (eds Steel, J. H., Turekian, K. K. & Thorpe, S. A.):3568-3576. DOI:10.1016/B978-012374473-9.00662-7
- Unger D, Ittekkot V and Schafer P, et al. (2003) Seasonality and interannual variability of particle fluxes to the deep Bay of Bengal: influence of riverine input and oceanographic processes. *Deep Sea Res. Part II* 50:897923. DOI:10.1016/S0967-0645(02)00612-4
- Vialard J, Jayakumar A and Gnanaseelan C, et al. (2012) Processes of 30-90 days sea surface temperature variability in the northern Indian Ocean during boreal summer. *Clim Dyn* 38 (9-10): 1901-1916. DOI:10.1007/s00382-011-1015-3
- Vinayachandran, P.N, Murty V.S.N and Ramesh Babu V, (2002) Observations of barrier layer formation in the Bay of Bengal during summer monsoon. *J Geophys Res Oceans* 107 (C12) SRF-19. DOI:10.1029/2001JC000831

- Vinayachandran PN (2009) Impact of physical processes on chlorophyll distribution in the Bay of Bengal. *Indian Ocean Biogeochemical Processes and Ecological Variability. Geophys Monogr Ser* 185:71–86. DOI:10.1029/2008GM000705
- Vijith V, Vinayachandran PN and Thushara V, et al. (2016) Consequences of inhibition of mixed-layer deepening by the West India Coastal Current for winter phytoplankton bloom in the northeastern Arabian Sea. *J Geophys Res Oceans* 121:6583–6603. DOI:10.1002/2016JC012004
- Wang P, Prell W, Blum P, et al. (2000) *Proceedings of Ocean Drilling Program. Initial Reports* 184, College Station, TX.
- Wang B, Clemens S and Liu P (2003) Contrasting the Indian and East Asian monsoons: implications on geologic time scale. *Marine Geology* 201:5–21. DOI:10.1016/S0025-3227(03)00196-8
- Webster PJ, Magana VO and Palmer TN, et al. (1998) Monsoons: processes, predictability, and the prospects for prediction. *Journal of Geophysical Research* 103 (C7):14451–14510. DOI:10.1029/97JC02719
- Weller RA, Baumgartner MF and Josey SA, et al. (1998) Atmospheric forcing in the Arabian Sea during 1994–1995: observations and comparisons with climatology and models. *Deep Sea Res. Part II* 45:1961–1999. DOI:10.1016/S0967-0645(98)00060-5
- Wiggert JD, Hoodb RR and Bansec K, et al. (2005) Monsoon-driven biogeochemical processes in the Arabian Sea. *Progress in Oceanography* 65:176–213. DOI:10.1016/j.pocean.2005.03.008
- Wiggert JD, Jones BH and Dickey TD, et al. (2000) The northeast monsoons impact on mixing, phytoplankton biomass and nutrient cycling in the Arabian Sea. *Deep-Sea Research II* 47:1353–1385. DOI:10.1016/S0967-0645(99)00147-2
- Wiggert JD, Murtugudde RG and McClain C R (2002) Processes controlling interannual variations in wintertime (Northeast Monsoon) primary productivity in the central Arabian Sea. *Deep-Sea Research II* 49:2319–2343. DOI:10.1016/S0967-0645(02)00039-5
- Winter A and Siesser WG (1994) *Coccolithophores*. Cambridge University Press 242.
- Wyrski K (1973) Physical oceanography of the Indian ocean. In: Zeitschel, B. (Ed.), *The Biology of the Indian Ocean*. Springer Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg, New York pp.18–36. DOI:10.1007/978-3-642-65468-8_3
- Xinquan Zhou, Stéphanie Duchamp-Alphonse and Masa Kageyama, et al. (2020) Dynamics of primary productivity in the northeastern Bay of Bengal over the last 26 000 years. *Climate of the Past* 16:1969–1986. DOI:10.5194/cp-16-1969-2020
- Young JR, Andrleit H and Probert I (2009) Coccolith function and morphogenesis, insights from appendage-bearing coccolithophores of the family Syracosphaeraceae (Haptophyta). *Journal of Phycology* 45:213–226. DOI:10.1111/j.1529-8817.2008.00643.x
- Young JR (1994) Functions of coccoliths. In *Coccolithophores* (eds Winter, A. and Siesser, W. G.) 63–82
- Yuki O, Junichiro K, Asuka Y, et al. (2019) Monsoon-influenced variations in plankton community structure and upper-water column stratification in the western Bay of Bengal during the past 80 ky. *Paleogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 521:138–150. DOI:10.1016/j.palaeo.2019.02.020

Author Contributions

NYL and MHR conceived the concept, wrote and approved the manuscript.

Acknowledgements

Not applicable.

Funding

Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials

Not applicable.

Competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

Open Access *This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution, and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third-party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons license unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons license and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. Visit for more details <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.*

Citation: Liza NY and Rahman MH (2025) Influence of Monsoon Dynamics and Oceanographic Conditions on Coccolithophores in the Indian Ocean. *Environmental Science Archives* 4(1): 21-34.